

THE STRUCTURAL ELEMENTS OF PROFESSIONAL CONSCIOUSNESS

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Annotation. The article analyzes the main components of professional consciousness, namely cognitive, emotional, motivational, value-normative, behavioral, reflexive, social-communicative, aesthetic, and spiritual components of professional consciousness, as well as the influence of professional knowledge, skills, motivation, and emotional stability on professional consciousness.

Keywords: professional consciousness, cognitive component, emotional component, motivational component, professional values, professional knowledge, professional qualifications, stress resistance, emotional stability, motivation, internal motives, external motives, professional development, professional ethics, attitude towards work, professional competence.

Professional consciousness is a complex psychological structure that encompasses mental processes, knowledge, skills, values, motives, and emotions in a person's professional activity. A deeper study of its structural elements is crucial for enhancing the effectiveness of employees' professional activities, ensuring professional development, and making a worthy contribution to society.

We will analyze the cognitive (knowledge) component as the primary structural element of professional consciousness. The cognitive component includes knowledge, concepts, thought processes, and thinking skills necessary for professional activity. This component ensures the employee's effective performance in their professional activities. B.S. Bloom, an American psychologist of educational methods, describes the stages of development of cognitive abilities, emphasizing the importance of professional knowledge as the fundamental foundation of professional activity.[1]

Professional knowledge is understood as the acquisition of in-depth knowledge in areas such as legislation, legal norms, methods of combating crime, operational-search activities, and investigative methodology, which are important for the service activities of internal affairs officers. The mandatory knowledge of laws and their observance by employees of internal affairs bodies are also enshrined in current regulatory legal acts. In particular, one of the main principles of the activities of internal affairs bodies, enshrined in Article 6 of the Law "On Internal Affairs Bodies," is the principle of legality, in which employees are obliged to strictly comply with the requirements of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Law "On Internal Affairs Bodies" and other legislative acts in their activities and comply with them.

In addition to professional knowledge, employees must also possess the ability to think quickly and clearly in complex situations, analyze, generalize, and draw conclusions. These

abilities, known as professional thinking, help employees discover crimes, identify and prevent offenders.

Another element of the cognitive component is the perception and processing of information. The current process of globalization and changes in public life and legislation require employees to quickly and effectively absorb new information and apply it in their professional activities.

Let's analyze the affective (emotional) component of the next element of professional consciousness. The affective component expresses a person's feelings and emotional attitude towards their professional activity. This component determines the employee's love of work, level of job satisfaction, and emotional stability. Let's consider the following features of the affective component:

emotional stability is the ability to control oneself in stressful and dangerous situations, maintaining emotional balance.[3] Emotional stability is especially important in situations that arise in the work of employees, leading to stress, as employees must be able to correctly react to difficulties in any situation and manage negative emotions.

empathy and emotional intelligence are the ability to understand the state of citizens, to be sensitive to their needs. According to paragraph 5 of the Code of "Professional Culture and Service Discipline of Internal Affairs Officers," an internal affairs officer should be polite, modest and restrained in communication with citizens, and not allow any person, group, or organization, regardless of social origin, economic status, and other factors, to be discriminated against or preferred.[4];

job satisfaction is the acquisition of moral satisfaction from professional activity, which increases employee motivation and improves work productivity.

The next element of professional consciousness is the motivational component, which reflects a person's aspirations, motives, needs, and interests in professional activity. This component includes a desire to achieve success in professional activity, a need for self-expression, and a desire for professional development. We can list the following characteristics of this component:

internal motives are patriotism, the desire to ensure justice, the desire to help people.[5] Internal motives are formed based on a person's own desires, interests, values, and goals, and determine their actions independently of external influences.

external motives - Material incentives, social status, rewards, and recognition. External motives typically influence a person's actions from the outside, and they act for a specific reward, benefit, or recognition;

ways to increase motivation include improving the incentive system and creating opportunities for professional growth. Significant reforms have been implemented in this area in recent years. In particular, the order of the Minister of Internal Affairs dated March 1, 2022 No. 55 "On further improvement of social protection activities in internal affairs bodies" was signed. Through this order, the goal was to further reduce bureaucratic barriers to employee social protection activities.[6]

The value-normative component encompasses the values, norms, rules of conduct, and ethical principles of a person in their professional activity. Let's consider the following features of this component:

professional values - the rule of law, justice, respect for human rights, service duty [7];

ethical norms - adherence to the rules of professional ethics, service discipline.

The Code of "Professional Culture and Service Discipline of Internal Affairs Officers" defines the norms of ethics, behavior in the service and relations with the public of an internal affairs officer [8];

social responsibility is a sense of responsibility to society, a desire to protect the rights and interests of citizens.

The behavioral component reflects a person's practical actions, skills, and abilities in professional activity. Let's consider the following characteristics of the behavioral component:

professional skills - practical skills in operational-search, investigation, crime detection, public order protection[9];

methods and techniques of work - the use of modern technologies, work with information systems, effective use of communication tools.

compliance of actions with the law - any practical action must be within the law and in accordance with ethical norms. Article 6 of the Law "On Internal Affairs Bodies" states that the activities of employees must strictly comply with the law.[10]

The reflective component expresses a person's desire to analyze their professional activity, self-assess, identify strengths and weaknesses, and develop them. The following are the characteristics of the reflective component:

- self-analysis - analyzing the results of activities, learning from mistakes, taking measures not to repeat them.[11];

professional development plan - creating personal plans for professional development, acquiring new knowledge and skills;

self-esteem and critical thinking are the ability to objectively evaluate one's work, to think critically.

The socio-communicative component reflects a person's ability to communicate in a professional community, teamwork skills, and relationships with the public. These are distinguished by the following features:

communication skills are the ability to communicate effectively and respectfully with people of different categories.

teamwork - working in collaboration with colleagues, effectively fulfilling their role in the team to achieve common goals;

public relations - gaining the trust of citizens, understanding their problems and helping them. Article 11 of the Law "On Internal Affairs Bodies" specifies the responsibilities of employees for effective interaction with the public.[13]

The aesthetic component reflects the aesthetic values of a person in their professional activity, their external appearance, service culture, and general aesthetic taste. The characteristics of the aesthetic component are as follows:

appearance - cleanliness, personal hygiene, and overall appearance of the employee's workwear. The order of the Minister of Internal Affairs "On Approving the Rules for Wearing Uniform Clothing in Internal Affairs Bodies" established the requirements for the uniform of employees.[14]

service culture - cleanliness of the workplace, accuracy and courtesy in working with documents;

aesthetic taste and culture are an interest in art, literature, and culture, which expands the employee's overall worldview.

We will analyze the spiritual component as the final structural element of professional consciousness. This component includes a person's spiritual values, conscience, beliefs, and human qualities. The characteristics of the spiritual component are as follows:

conscience and responsibility - to act in accordance with laws and human norms, to feel responsible for one's actions;

human qualities are compassion, compassion, justice, patriotism[15].

Based on the opinions and considerations analyzed above, the following can be included in the main structural elements of professional consciousness:

the cognitive (knowledge) component;

affective component;

the motivational component;

the value-normative component;

the behavioral component;

reflexive component;

the socio-communicative component;

aesthetic component;

spiritual component.

The structural elements of professional consciousness are closely interconnected, and their strength and harmony ensure the effectiveness of the professional activities of employees. For employees of internal affairs bodies, each of these components is of great importance. The cognitive component reflects knowledge and skills, the affective component - emotions, the motivational component - aspirations and motives, the value-normative component - morals and values, the behavioral component - practical actions, the reflexive component - self-analysis, the socio-communicative component - communication and social relations, the aesthetic component - service culture, and the spiritual component - human qualities.

The professional consciousness of employees is enhanced through the development and strengthening of these structural elements, which is crucial for ensuring the rule of law, maintaining public safety, and protecting the rights of citizens. Normative legal acts and scientific literature provide the foundations and recommendations necessary for the development of these elements of professional consciousness.

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